

Current Trends in Management and Its Strategies

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Abstract

There are many new ways to learn and perform. Everyone’s roles will transform the work environment. Many things have been invented and developed in HR domain due to technological development. There are many updates and many trends in management. Globalization and market conditions make organizations to practice change in their way. Organizational Change is latest trend in the management era. Organizational Change is a process of transforming its workforce and non-human resources to future state from the existing state. It helps the organization to withstand in the competitive market. This paper addresses latest trends in organizational change.

Keywords: Issues and Challenges, Trends and Practices, Major influencing factors Etc.

Introduction

HR Strategy is developed after analyzing industry characters, competitive advantage and personnel. Strategies may be developed according to skills, knowledge and responsibilities of different groups of employees. It may be necessary for company’s peace. The Strategy should take in account of organization’s culture, structure and people.

Principles of the HR Strategy

- Considers employees as valuable assets.
- Recognizes the employees role in the working environment.
- Recognizes the relationships between people management and performance of the college.
- Assures to retain well qualified and well-motivated staffs for the success of the organization.

Human Resource Management (HRM)

Human Resource Management refers recruiting people, maintaining, creating policies and procedures. It influences employees’ performances. HRM includes some practices. Those are HR planning, recruitment, selection, training and development, compensation & reward and performance appraisal and maintaining

industrial relations. The above mentioned practices support the organization's objectives and goals. Effective and Efficient HR Department enhances performance of the organization through contribution of employees, customers satisfaction, innovation, increased productivity and good. HRM activities widely recognized in all aspects.

HR Department Challenges

Challenge is common to all in their routine life. HR department is also not exempted. Among increased competition in the market, HR Department has to recruit and select right candidate to support the organization for attaining the goals. Some skills are highly importance nowadays for sustaining in the competitive environment. Organizations fail if its workforces are not up to the mark. There are many job seekers in the industry. But the question is, Are they skilled? Answer is NO. Because new entrants in job market do not have required skills to perform the tasks in the company.

Some skills are highly required. Those are communication, language, computer, problem solving, team leading, innovative, organizational learning. Lack of required skills in employees will affect productivity of the company and the same will reflect in the company's profit. Many employees face difficulties to find out the suitable and adroit job applicant in the market.

How HR Can Master Strategy

HR plays important role in formulating business strategy. Particularly HR considers workforce as assets of the company. Many people think that CEOs decision does only help the organization to grow. But only a few knows HR Department plays crucial role in company's achievement. Researchers found that 70% of Chief Executive Officers recognize HR Department role in organization's success. They discuss HR before implementing any type of policies. Because tasks are done by the human beings in major. So HR Department is recognized in formulation of any policies related to any department in the company.

Competitive Advantage - Industry Perspective

A company can have competitive advantage through two strategies. One is Cost Reduction and another one is Product differentiation. Cost reduction can be reached by producing similar products in high numbers. So cost of production will come down. The company can sell many products and reap benefits. On other hand, if company produces different products, customers base may increase. Many customers will try to buy and use different products. Through this strategy company may sell many differentiated products to customers and gain profit. But there is a difficulty in product differentiation strategy. It increases costs.

The above mentioned two strategies can be obtained through human resources. Effective and efficient human resources will try to use their skills to cut down the costs by applying their innovative skills and problem solving skills. And marketing personnel will use their communication skill to lure the customers towards the products of their company.

Corporate Strategy

Corporate strategy means the overall strategy of the company. It supports the organization to grow up in the competitive environment. Corporate strategy is formed by taking account of internal and external compliances. Technologies and humans are taken account. It is framed to achieve the goals and keeping objectives of the company on track.

Types of HR Strategies

HR Strategies differ in all organizations. Nothing is standardized in HR Strategies.

Armstrong and Long conducted research exposed many variations. A few strategies are exposing general declarations and rest of them goes in detail. But there are two types of HR Strategies which relate the different aspects of Human Resource Management. One is Overarching Strategy and another one is Specific Strategy.

Overarching HR strategies: This type of strategy denotes the general objective and intentions of the company about the people management. It explains how the workforce should be managed, developed, retained, motivated and engaged in the working environment.

Overarching strategies describe the general intentions of the organization about how people should be managed and developed and what steps should be taken to ensure that the organization can attract and retain the people it needs and ensure so far as possible that employees are committed, motivated and engaged.

Specific Strategy

Specific strategy refers to concentrate on particular department or domain. It focuses on each activity of human resource management. There may be a specific strategy for recruitment. It may express how to recruit, where to recruit, whom to recruit, recruitment cost, recruitment source.

These two strategies attempt to create good place to work.

The following are some examples of overarching HR strategy statements

B&Q: Enhance employee commitment and minimize the loss of B&Q’s best people

GlaxoSmithKline (gsk): We want GSK to be a place where the best people do their best work.

Most Prominent Management Trends of the 21St Century

1. Globalization

Globalization is current trend in organizational change. Globalization refers free movement of goods, services, ideas, money, materials, technology from border to border. Today, companies are operating in global environment where high competition is existing.

2. Technology

Technology plays vital role in organizational change. It is updated in every minute. Human efforts in the company have been reduced by applying technology in the working area. After arrival of technology in all industry, human value has been losing significantly. HR Department is most cautious in recruiting employees. Employees are required competitive skills to perform their tasks by using their technological skills.

3. Sustainability and Corporate Social Responsibility

In order to sustain the competitive environment, the company has to apply management strategies in social activities. By depleting natural resources, the company losses its raw material and affects natural environment. It has to pay back to the society by giving some amount from the profit to the society. Moreover the company has to spend on environmental sustainability and energy security. It provides access to healthcare for the employees. Through this strategy, the company will gain goodwill in the society.

4. The Study of Psychology

There are many interdisciplinary in the business. Studying the human minds is important in the business environment. Because the company will have to deal to with human beings for manufacturing and selling the products. Humans are involved in buying and selling process. By reading the people mind, the company can understand the needs of the customers and employees. Psychology helps to motivate the employees.

5. Business Ecosystems

Professor Carlyss Y. Baldwin feels that one of the most notable trends in management has been the rise of business ecosystems - defined as groups of firms which together provide complex products and related services to meet end-to-end requirements of users across the value chain. The integration between media, technology and telecommunication firms would be an apt contemporary example. It has important implications for management because innovation in business ecosystems has a character distinct from traditional, vertically integrated firms. Every organization in the ecosystem has to be aware of the bigger picture. As Professor Baldwin tells Working Knowledge, Innovation in ecosystems requires collective action to both invent and appraise, efficient, cross-organization knowledge flows, modular architectures, and good stewardship of legacy systems. It rests on multiple complementary platforms.

Conclusion

This paper finally concludes from the above discussion that all the five trends of organizational change produce results in greater organizational or system complexity for both leaders and employees in organizations. The tensions created by these trends cannot be removed. They have to be managed. Effective approaches in organizational change will involve not one strategy, but many alternatives will require leaders and employees to develop greater resilience in confronting these tensions.

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